

21st CENTURY TEACHING STRATEGIES AND TEACHING PERFORMANCE AMONG SOCIAL STUDIES TEACHERS IN CALAMBA CITY PRIVATE SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This study was intended to determine the relationship between 21st Century Teaching Strategies and Teaching Performance among Social Studies teachers in Calamba City private schools. It aimed to explore the utilization of various 21st Century Teaching Strategies, including Gen A Teaching Strategies, Evidence Based/High Impact and Kagan Learning Structure. The study did not only provide a comprehensive overview of the current practices and performance levels but also examined the correlations between different teaching strategies and their impact on teaching performance. The implementation of the 21st century teaching strategies among Social Studies teachers in terms of Gen A Teaching Strategies was Fully Implemented (3.50). The implementation of 21st century teaching strategies among Social Studies teachers in terms of active learning, cooperative learning, formative assessment, differentiated instructions, and classroom discussion was Fully Implemented (3.55). The implementation of 21st century teaching strategies among Social Studies teachers in terms of round table, quiz - quiz trade, timed-pair share, fan n share, and numbered heads together was Fully Implemented (3.51). Teaching performance level among Social Studies teachers in Calamba City private schools in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy was Very Good (3.56). The teaching performance level among Social Studies teachers in terms of learning environment was Very Good (3.75). Moreover, a significant correlation was found between the teaching performance of Social Studies teachers and 21st-century teaching strategies. The probability values of 0.000, which is less than the significance level of .05. An enhancement program for teaching strategies of Social Studies teachers in Calamba City private schools was proposed.

Keywords: *21st century teaching strategies, teaching performance, Gen A teaching strategies, evidence based/high impact learning structure, Kagan Learning Structure*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching had long been esteemed as a profession crucial to shaping future generations. Education, an ever-evolving field, demanded that educators be innovative and adaptable to meet changing student needs. The 21st century introduced new teaching methods to enhance knowledge transfer and student engagement, highlighting the importance of modern approaches to maintain relevance and effectiveness (University of the People, 2024).

In response to rapid societal changes, 21st-century teaching methods evolved significantly. Teachers emphasized technology, critical thinking, creativity, and teamwork, focusing on student-centered learning through group projects, inquiry-based tasks, and problem-solving. Digital tools and online resources revolutionized education, while flipped classrooms and personalized learning catered to individual needs, allowing students to progress at their own pace. Professional development was crucial for implementing these strategies, greatly impacting educators' effectiveness and student success (Ranjan, 2023).

This highlighted the need for private social studies teachers to integrate 21st-century methodologies. Understanding their challenges and opportunities was essential for identifying necessary professional development. Addressing this gap provided valuable insights for educators and policymakers, advancing educational practices in the 21st century (Kim, 2019).

The teaching profession played a key role in developing individuals with integrity, knowledge, and capabilities, long recognized for its societal impact. Since the early 21st century, teaching methods evolved, prompting teachers to adapt to the needs of tech-savvy students. Employing 21st-century strategies was crucial for creating dynamic, successful learning environments that catered to diverse student needs (Mugabo, 2020).

Given students' intrinsic association with digital technologies, conventional teaching approaches were insufficient in the 21st century. As more individuals became proficient with digital tools from a young age, expectations changed. Educators had to adapt by integrating technology into the classroom, a task that required more than just adding tech; it necessitated professional development programs to equip teachers with the skills needed to enhance learning outcomes (Yeboah, 2020).

There was a strong correlation between adopting modern teaching methods in the 21st century and teaching excellence. Educators who used technology and innovative methods enhanced learning experiences, but many-faced challenges due to lack of familiarity, underscoring the need for focused professional development (Munna, 2021). This was especially true in 21st-century social studies education within private schools in

Calamba City, where research on improved teacher performance had been lacking despite the potential for innovative methods to revolutionize education (Al-Ghasab, 2022).

Addressing this research gap was crucial for enhancing understanding of effective teaching practices and impacting teacher preparation programs and curriculum design. Examining how social studies teachers in private schools utilized modern teaching techniques in the 21st century revealed obstacles, advancements, and their impact on student development. This research aimed to identify strategies for supporting teachers, enhancing graduate quality, and preparing students for the complexities of contemporary society (Podolsky, 2019). It was crucial to bridge the gap between traditional teaching methods and the demands of the 21st century. Focusing on social studies teachers in private schools, the study explored the challenges of adopting modern teaching methods and their benefits for student performance and teacher effectiveness.

Specifically, this study addresses the research gap concerning 21st-century teaching strategies in social studies education within private schools in Calamba City. It examines how these strategies are implemented by social studies teachers, evaluates their impact on student performance, and identifies the associated challenges. The findings aim to enhance education quality by recommending advancements in professional development, teaching methodologies, and educational policies (Mallilin, 2021). Given the dynamic landscape of 21st-century education, the study also investigates the correlation between teacher effectiveness and these contemporary methods. Its goal is to promote effective teaching practices that foster conducive learning environments and align with evolving educational needs (Ononiwu, 2023).

Research Questions

This study was intended to determine the relationship between 21st Century Teaching Strategies and Teaching Performance among Social Studies Teachers in the Private Schools of Calamba City, Laguna.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of implementation of the 21st Century teaching strategies among Social Studies teachers in Calamba City private schools in terms of:
 - 1.1 Gen A Teaching Strategies,
 - 1.2 Evidence Based-High Impact, and
 - 1.3 Kagan Learning Structure?

2. What is the teaching performance level among Social Studies teachers in Calamba City private schools in terms of:
 - 2.1 Content Knowledge and Pedagogy,
 - 2.2 Learning Environment,
 - 2.3 Diversity of Learners,

2.4 Curriculum Planning,
2.5 Assessment and Reporting, and
2.6 Community Linkages and Professional Engagement?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation of 21st Century Teaching Strategies and teaching performance level of Social Studies teachers in Calamba City private schools?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what enhancement program for Social Studies teachers in Calamba City Private Schools may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the methodology of the study including research design, respondents of the study, sampling technique, research instrument, validation of instrument and research procedure.

Research Design

The descriptive-correlational design, as defined by research experts, was a methodological approach used to describe the variables of interest and examine the relationships that naturally occurred between them. This design was particularly suited for studies aiming to explore associations between variables without manipulating them, thus providing insights into existing patterns and connections within a given context. In the context of this study, the descriptive-correlational design enabled researchers to systematically describe the extent of 21st-century Teaching Strategies and Teaching Performance among Social Studies teachers in Calamba City Private Schools. By employing this design, the study not only provided a comprehensive overview of the current practices and performance levels but also examined the correlations between different teaching strategies.

This method was taken into great consideration because, according to Creswell (2018), as cited in Walters, (2020) descriptive correlation research focuses on describing and understanding relationships between variables. Walters also emphasized that this method involves detailed analysis and interpretation of existing conditions, and often includes comparisons, contrasts, and the exploration of relationships between variables. A descriptive correlation study should be unbiased, aiming to collect factual evidence and information to provide a comprehensive understanding of the subject. Writing a descriptive correlation study can be challenging due to its reliance on unbiased data collection and analysis, but it is a valuable approach commonly used in various fields to analyze relationships between different phenomena.

The choice of the descriptive-correlational design aligned with the study's objectives and direction by allowing researchers to explore the relationship between 21st-century teaching strategies and teaching performance among Social Studies teachers.

Through the systematic description of variables and examination of correlations, the study aimed to identify the extent to which 21st-century Teaching Strategies were implemented and their association with teaching performance in the context of Calamba City Private Schools. By understanding these relationships, the study sought to inform strategies for enhancing teaching practices, improving student outcomes, and promoting effective instructional approaches tailored to the needs of 21st-century learners. Thus, the descriptive-correlational design served as a suitable methodological framework for achieving the study's objectives and advancing knowledge in the field of education.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines with the selected basic education institution operating in the said city. The selected Basic Education Institutions are Saint Benilde International School, Little Jesus Learning Center Canlubang and Philippine Women's University (Calamba).

Population and Sampling

The population for this study comprised social studies teachers and their students in Calamba City Private Schools. Sampling was conducted using stratified random sampling, a method that was relatively straightforward to implement as it only required a single random selection and minimal prior knowledge of the population. This approach ensured strong internal and external validity in the research, reducing the likelihood of sampling bias and selection bias (Hall, 2020).

The research population included three Basic Education Institutions in Calamba City, consisting of social studies teachers and their students for the School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, it involved sixteen (16) social studies teachers and one hundred ten (110) students, totaling 126 respondents. The study used G Power to determine the number of respondents, which was 126, with an effect size of 0.31 and a confidence level of 95%.

Respondents of the Study

The study involved Social Studies teachers and their students from private schools in Calamba City, Laguna, as respondents. This study employed a stratified simple random sampling technique, focusing on Social Studies teachers and their students to evaluate their teaching strategies and performance. The inclusion of both teachers and students aimed to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the teaching process, including the impact of teaching strategies on student outcomes.

Instrument

The research instrument consisted of rigorously developed survey questionnaires tailored precisely to correspond with the objectives and research questions specified in Chapter 1 of the study. Each component of the instrument aligned with a particular feature

of the Statement of the Problem, ensuring a thorough examination of the study's main areas of focus.

Part 1 of the instrument, a researcher-made questionnaire, was designed based on the first research question. It specifically evaluated the degree to which Social Studies teachers in Calamba City Private Schools utilized 21st-century teaching strategies. This section included topics relevant to several teaching tactics used in the 21st century, including Gen A Teaching Strategies, evidence-based, high-impact, and Kagan approaches. Teachers and students were requested to specify the frequency at which they utilized these strategies in their teaching methodologies.

Part 2 of the instrument consisted of an adapted questionnaire from the DepEd Order No. 42 s, 2017 entitled "National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. This part focused on measuring teaching performance among Social Studies teachers, specifically addressing the second research question. It covered teaching performance indicators mentioned in the Statement of the Problem, such as content knowledge pedagogy, learning environment, diversity of learners, curriculum planning, assessment and reporting, community linkages, and professional engagement.

Teachers were required to evaluate their effectiveness in each of these categories based on their own perceptions and experiences. By organizing the research instrument in this way, each section directly related to a certain component of the research questions, making it easier to systematically and thoroughly evaluate the main topics of the study. This methodology guaranteed that the gathered data specifically targeted the research objectives stated in Chapter 01, allowing the researcher to derive significant conclusions and insights regarding the correlation between 21st-century teaching strategies and teaching performance among Social Studies teachers in Calamba City Private Schools.

Validation of the Instrument

The questionnaires underwent a rigorous validation process involving both internal and external validators, including three experts from within the institution and three external experts in research. Their feedback on relevance and clarity was carefully considered, leading to necessary revisions. After incorporating essential changes based on their input, the finalized questionnaires were meticulously prepared for data collection. The Content Validity Ratio (CVR) scores were 1.0 and 0.99, indicating high validity. Additionally, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which assessed reliability, yielded a satisfactory score of 0.70. A pilot test with 20 respondents further confirmed the questionnaire's internal consistency. The researcher had developed the instrument independently, and the final draft had been ready for pilot testing at Asian Computer College in Calamba City, Laguna.

Data Gathering Procedure

In the pre-data gathering phase, meticulous steps were taken to ensure the ethical and methodological integrity of the study. This involved obtaining necessary permissions

from relevant authorities, such as school administrators and local education boards, to conduct research within Calamba City Private Schools. Following this, the researcher embarked on the development and validation of survey questionnaires tailored to assess the identified variables and objectives of the study. These questionnaires underwent rigorous scrutiny through expert validation involving both internal and external validators, aimed at enhancing their reliability and validity.

Moreover, the informed consent process was diligently carried out, ensuring that all participating Social Studies teachers were fully aware of the study's purpose, their rights as participants, and the voluntary nature of their involvement. This ethical foundation was crucial in fostering trust and cooperation among participants and upholding the principles of research integrity throughout the study.

Moving to the data-gathering phase, the finalized survey questionnaires were disseminated among the targeted sample of Social Studies teachers within Calamba City Private Schools. Researchers either personally administered the surveys during scheduled visits to each school or coordinated with school administrators for the distribution process. This phase required meticulous coordination and adherence to protocols to ensure that data collection proceeded smoothly and efficiently. Once data collection was complete, the responses from the survey questionnaires were carefully compiled and tabulated in a systematic manner, laying the groundwork for subsequent data analysis.

Additionally, all completed survey forms were securely stored to protect the confidentiality of participants' responses and maintain the integrity of the data. Throughout these phases, transparency, professionalism, and ethical conduct remained paramount, reflecting the commitment of the research team to uphold the highest standards of research practice.

RESULTS

Research Question 1. What is the level of implementation of the 21st Century teaching strategies among Social Studies teachers in Calamba City private schools in terms of:

1.1 Gen A Teaching Strategies

Table 1.1

Level of Implementation of the 21st Century Teaching Strategies among Social Studies Teachers in terms of Gen A Teaching Strategies

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
1. Integration of Technology	3.44	FI	3.49	FI	3.47	FI

2. Personalization and Differentiation	3.44	FI	3.46	FI	3.45	FI
3. Collaboration and Communication	3.63	FI	3.49	FI	3.56	FI
4. Multimodal and Interactive Learning	3.56	FI	3.52	FI	3.54	FI
5. Real-World Relevance and Application.	3.50	FI	3.50	FI	3.50	FI
General Composite Assessment	3.51	FI	3.49	FI	3.50	FI

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree - Fully Implemented (FI) 1.75-2.49 Disagree - Partially Implemented (PI)
2.50-3.24 Agree - Implemented (I) 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree - Not Implemented (NI)

1.2. Evidence Based-High Impact

Table 1.2

Level of Implementation of the 21st Century Teaching Strategies among Social Studies Teachers in Calamba City Private Schools in terms of Evidence Base/High Impact Teaching Strategies

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
1. Active Learning	3.53	FI	3.54	FI	3.54	FI
2. Cooperative Learning	3.53	FI	3.49	FI	3.51	FI
3. Formative Assessment	3.58	FI	3.51	FI	3.55	FI
4. Differentiated Instructions	3.45	FI	3.48	FI	3.47	FI
5. Classroom Discussion	3.83	FI	3.52	FI	3.68	FI
General Composite Assessment	3.59	FI	3.51	FI	3.55	FI

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree - Fully Implemented (FI) 1.75-2.49 Disagree - Partially Implemented (PI)
2.50-3.24 Agree - Implemented (I) 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree - Not Implemented (NI)

1.3 Kagan Learning Structure

Table 1.3

Level of Implementation of the 21st Century Teaching Strategies among Social Studies Teachers in Calamba City Private Schools in terms of Kagan Learning Structure

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
1. Round Table	3.75	FI	3.54	FI	3.65	FI
2. Quiz – Quiz Trade	3.50	FI	3.52	FI	3.51	FI
3. Timed-Pair Share	3.78	FI	3.49	FI	3.64	FI
4. Fan N Share	3.75	FI	3.50	FI	3.63	FI
5. Numbered Heads Together	3.75	FI	3.50	FI	3.63	FI
General Composite Assessment	3.71	FI	3.51	FI	3.61	FI

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Strongly Agree - Fully Implemented (FI) 1.75-2.49 Disagree - Partially Implemented (PI)
2.50-3.24 Agree - Implemented (I) 1.00-1.74 Strongly Disagree - Not Implemented (NI)

Research Question 2. What is the teaching performance level among Social Studies teachers in Calamba City private schools in terms of:

2.1 Content Knowledge and Pedagogy
Table 2.1

Teaching Performance Level among Social Studies Teachers in Calamba City Private Schools in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
1. Using effective information and communication technology in teaching.	3.81	VG	3.54	VG	3.68	VG
2. Using varied teaching strategies for the 21 st century learners.	3.75	VG	3.43	VG	3.59	VG
3. Updating content knowledge through latest research findings and principles in teaching.	3.81	VG	3.48	VG	3.65	VG
4. Developing contextualized and localized instructional materials.	3.69	VG	3.50	VG	3.60	VG
5. Conducting and writing research papers	3.25	VG	3.37	VG	3.31	VG
General Composite Assessment	3.66	VG	3.46	VG	3.56	VG

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F)
2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Good (G) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Poor (P)

2.2 Learning Environment
Table 2.2

Teaching Performance Level among Social Studies Teachers in Calamba City Private Schools in terms of Learning Environment

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
1. Maintaining learner’s proper discipline in the class.	3.88	VG	3.61	VG	3.75	VG
2. Increasing learners’ participation through motivational activities	3.88	VG	3.49	VG	3.69	VG
3. Promoting fairness, respect, and care among learners	4.00	VG	3.59	VG	3.80	VG
4. Handling learners’ misbehaviors.	3.88	VG	3.53	VG	3.71	VG
5. Building a harmonious relationship among learners	4.00	VG	3.61	VG	3.81	VG
General Composite Assessment	3.93	VG	3.57	VG	3.75	VG

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F)
2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Good (G) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Poor (P)

2.3 Diversity of Learners

Table 2.3

Teaching Performance Level among Social Studies Teachers in Calamba City Private Schools in terms of Diversity of Learners

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
1. Using different teaching strategies responsive to varied learners.	3.75	VG	3.45	VG	3.60	VG
2. Giving the right approach for learners with giftedness and difficulties.	3.81	VG	3.48	VG	3.65	VG
3. Handling learners with special needs.	3.44	VG	3.45	VG	3.45	VG
4. Developing appropriate strategies inclusive for indigenous learners.	3.69	VG	3.42	VG	3.56	VG
5. Handling learners in difficult circumstances like disaster, chronic illness, etc.	3.81	VG	3.46	VG	3.64	VG
General Composite Assessment	3.70	VG	3.45	VG	3.58	VG

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F)
 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Good (G) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Poor (P)

2.4 Curriculum Planning

Table 2.4

Teaching Performance Level among Social Studies Teachers in Calamba City Private Schools in terms of Curriculum Planning

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
1. Using variety of resources such as technology to attain learning objectives.	3.81	VG	3.50	VG	3.66	VG
2. Updating and learning the current trends in education curriculum.	3.80	VG	3.55	VG	3.68	VG
3. Collaborating with other professionals to enrich knowledge and learning practice.	3.80	VG	3.44	VG	3.62	VG
4. Aligning teaching methods and assessment tools to learning objectives.	3.87	VG	3.54	VG	3.71	VG
5. Developing effective lesson plans.	3.80	VG	3.47	VG	3.64	VG
General Composite Assessment	3.78	VG	3.50	VG	3.64	VG

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F)
 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Good (G) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Poor (P)

2.5 Assessment and Reporting

Table 2.5

Teaching Performance Level among Social Studies Teachers in Calamba City Private Schools in terms of Assessment and Reporting

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
1. Using a variety of assessment tools appropriate for varied learners.	3.75	VG	3.55	VG	3.65	VG
2. Performing test validity, reliability, and item analysis for quality assessment	3.75	VG	3.55	VG	3.65	VG
3. Monitoring and evaluating students' progress and achievement.	3.81	VG	3.51	VG	3.66	VG
4. Using assessment data to improve classroom practice and learning.	3.81	VG	3.55	VG	3.68	VG
5. Effective feed-backing on learners' performance	3.81	VG	3.46	VG	3.64	VG
General Composite Assessment	3.79	VG	3.53	VG	3.66	VG

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F)
 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Good (G) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Poor (P)

2.6 Community Linkages and Professional Engagement

Table 2.6

Teaching Performance Level among Social Studies Teachers in Calamba City Private Schools in terms of Community Linkages and Professional Engagement

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
1. Involving parents in their child's education.	3.75	VG	3.38	VG	3.57	VG
2. Linking with government agencies to promote learners' welfare.	3.25	VG	3.47	VG	3.36	VG
3. Contextualizing the lessons in the subject being taught.	3.81	VG	3.47	VG	3.64	VG
4. Learning best practices for a good relationship among school, home, and community.	3.75	VG	3.51	VG	3.63	VG
5. Learning the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers.	3.88	VG	3.50	VG	3.69	VG
General Composite Assessment	3.69	VG	3.47	VG	3.58	VG

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F)
 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Good (G) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree - Poor (P)

Research Question 3. Is there a significant relationship between 21st Century Teaching Strategies and teaching performance of Social Studies teachers in Calamba City private schools?

Table 3

Test of Significant Relationship between the 21st Century Teaching Strategies and Teaching Performance of Social Studies Teacher in Calamba City Private Schools

21st Century Teaching Strategies	Teaching Performance of Social Studies Teacher	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Generation Alpha	Knowledge Content	.724**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Learning Environment	.641**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Diversity of Learners	.677**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Curriculum Planning	.677**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Assessment and Reporting	.700**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Community Linkages	.687**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
Evidence Based-High impact	Knowledge Content	.772**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Learning Environment	.665**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Diversity of Learners	.665**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Curriculum Planning	.625**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Assessment and Reporting	.705**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Community Linkages	.698**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
Kagan Learning Structure	Knowledge Content	.785**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Learning Environment	.716**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Diversity of Learners	.704**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Curriculum Planning	.686**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Assessment and Reporting	.754**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Community Linkages	.753**	.000	Significant	Reject ho

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

DISCUSSION

1.1 Gen A Teaching Strategies

Table 1.1

Level of Implementation of the 21st Century Teaching Strategies among Social Studies Teachers in terms of Gen A Teaching Strategies

The 21st Century teaching strategies among Social Studies Teachers in terms of Gen A Teaching Strategies was **Fully Implemented (3.50)**. “Collaboration and Communication” which yielded the highest mean score of 3.56 and was interpreted as **Fully Implemented**. However, the indicator “Personalization and Differentiation” yielded the lowest mean scores of 3.45 and was verbally interpreted as **Fully Implemented**.

It implies that teachers are actively addressing students' changing needs through their teaching approaches, recognizing that these demands include critical thinking, problem-solving, digital literacy, and global awareness. This can suggest a dedication to ongoing development and remaining up to date with the finest techniques in teaching. Rather to treating students as passive consumers of knowledge, the emphasis is probably on developing an interesting and dynamic learning environment where they participate actively in their education.

Accordingly, Sewell (2023) mentioned that a substantial change in educational practices and priorities was indicated by the news that social studies professors would be fully implementing 21st-century teaching strategies. By adopting these cutting-edge strategies, teachers radically altered the educational process for their pupils rather than just updating their lesson plans. The complete application of these tactics demonstrated a dedication to fairness and inclusivity in the classroom, going beyond academic preparation. Teachers could better support students with different learning styles and requirements by utilizing technology and a variety of teaching approaches. This guaranteed that all students, regardless of background or ability, had access to high-quality education. Essentially, social studies instructors who fully adopted 21st-century teaching techniques embarked on a revolutionary journey toward more inclusive, dynamic, and student-centered learning environments.

1.2. Evidence Based-High Impact

The 21st Century Teaching Strategies among Social Studies Teachers in terms of Evidence Base/High Impact Teaching Strategies was **Fully Implemented (3.55)** “Classroom Discussion” which yielded the highest mean score of 3.68 was interpreted as **Fully Implemented**. However, the indicator “Active Learning” yielded the lowest mean scores of 3.42 and was verbally interpreted as **Fully Implemented**.

It suggests that this interaction creates a climate in which dissenting viewpoints are valued and even encouraged since they deepen conversations on difficult subjects. The tone for classroom conversations is established by teachers who value courteous communication. Students are more inclined to act respectfully toward their peers when they see their teachers acting that way. This encourages tolerance and open-mindedness by creating a space where people with different viewpoints can voice them without worrying about being mocked or judged.

In the study by Mallilin (2021), students' critical thinking abilities were developed through the effective use of various tactics such as inquiry-based learning and cooperative group projects. This created an environment where different points of view were valued as important contributions to conversations and understanding, rather than merely tolerated. Teachers set the tone for interactions in the classroom by emphasizing polite discourse, which encouraged students to voice their thoughts without worrying about being judged. Additionally, these teaching methods frequently fostered collaboration, helping students understand the value of different viewpoints and benefit from each other. Ultimately, by nurturing these abilities, teachers not only improved

academic learning but also empowered students to become engaged, courteous members of a democratic society capable of earnestly engaging with opposing views and making valuable contributions to their communities.

1.3 Kagan Learning Structure

The 21st Century Teaching Strategies among Social Studies Teachers in terms of Kagan Learning Structure was **Fully Implemented (3.61)**. “Time Paired Share” which yielded the highest mean score of 3.71 and was interpreted as **Fully Implemented**. However, the indicator “Quiz-Quiz Trade” yielded the lowest mean scores of 3.51 and was verbally interpreted as **Fully Implemented**.

It implies that in establishing a classroom culture based on mutual respect and understanding can be achieved through encouraging attentiveness and appreciation for the contributions of peers. This fosters a culture of open communication and teamwork among the pupils. Active listening encourages a greater comprehension of the subject matter being covered. A deeper learning experience results when students genuinely interact with the contributions of their peers. This increases the likelihood that they will understand various viewpoints, ideas, and concepts. Students who actively listen to others are able to comprehend the perspectives and experiences of others, which promotes empathy. Additionally, it gives children the confidence and self-esteem they need by empowering them to feel heard and validated.

In LaMorte (2022), students gained essential skills that they could use both inside and outside of the classroom as they actively practiced listening. Additionally, encouraging active listening made students more engaged in class discussions and fostered a lively atmosphere where various perspectives were discussed and examined. Finally, allowing children to comprehend and value several points of view while feeling heard and validated promoted empathy and empowerment. In conclusion, encouraging active listening developed social and emotional competencies that were essential for success in a variety of spheres of life, in addition to improving academic learning.

Research Question 2. What is the teaching performance level among Social Studies teachers in Calamba City private schools in terms of:

2.1 Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

The teaching performance level among Social Studies Teachers as to Content Knowledge and Pedagogy was **Very Good (3.56)**. The indicator “Using effective information and communication technology in teaching” obtained the highest mean score of 3.68 and was interpreted as **Very Good**. However, the indicator “Conducting and writing research papers” yielded the lowest mean scores of 3.31 and was verbally interpreted as **Very Good**.

It indicates it is advantageous to use information and communication technology (ICT) into instructional strategies. The high mean indicates that ICT improves educational outcomes when used wisely. Higher levels of student engagement and interaction with the curriculum is probably fostered by effective ICT use. This could be accomplished through virtual simulations, internet forums, interactive multimedia content, etc. A more productive and efficient learning environment for both teachers and students may also result from effective ICT integration. Using technology may make tasks like grading, giving feedback, and obtaining information more efficient.

In relation to Clavarall (2022), this accomplishment showed how well ICT integration worked and its positive impact on various facets of education. Teachers who used ICT effectively experienced increased student involvement, interaction, and satisfaction with the educational process. Furthermore, it indicated that education became more flexible, accessible, and personalized for each student. Additionally, by streamlining tasks such as grading and access to resources, efficient ICT integration boosted productivity and efficiency for both educators and students. Moreover, prioritizing ICT in the classroom equipped students with critical thinking and digital literacy skills, which are essential for navigating the challenges of the digital age.

2.2 Learning Environment

The teaching performance level among Social Studies Teachers as to Learning Environment was Very Good (3.75). The indicator "Building a harmonious relationship among learners" attained the highest mean score of 3.81 and was interpreted as Very Good. However, the indicator "Increasing learners' participation through motivational activities" attained the lowest mean scores of 3.69 and was verbally interpreted as Very Good.

It implies that educators in this field are skilled at successfully imparting their subject matter. They probably employ a variety of instructional techniques, materials, and approaches to get kids interested in learning. A "very good" learning environment suggests that students are motivated, at ease, and encouraged while they pursue their education. Students are encouraged to participate, work together, and think critically in this encouraging environment. Higher levels of student engagement and accomplishment are frequently correlated with a supportive learning environment. When students perceive that their learning environment is encouraging and stimulating, they are more likely to pay attention, participate actively in class, and be driven to learn.

In accordance with Kagan (2024), a high degree of teaching effectiveness could only be attained by educators working together, continuing their professional development, and being open to modifying their lesson plans to better suit the needs of a varied student body. The statement subtly acknowledged the work of the school administration, teachers, and support personnel in creating a conducive learning environment by praising the quality of Social Studies teachers in this area. It underscored the significance of prioritizing the learning environment and the caliber of instruction in

educational institutions. This was evidence of the commitment of teachers and the transformational potential of effective teaching methods in shaping students' futures.

2.3 Diversity of Learners

The teaching performance level among Social Studies Teachers as to **Diversity of Learners** was **Very Good (3.58)**. The indicator “Giving the right approach for learners with giftedness and difficulties” gained the highest mean score of 3.65 and was interpreted as **Very Good**. However, the indicator “Handling learners with special needs” garnered the lowest mean scores of 3.45 and was verbally interpreted as **Very Good**.

It implies that these educators are skilled at modifying their lesson plans, resources, and strategies to suit the needs of pupils with different learning preferences, backgrounds, and skill levels. In order to create an inclusive learning environment where all students can succeed despite their differences, this is essential. It also speaks well of the instructors' dedication to meeting the educational demands of a varied student body and their professional abilities.

In line with Alvarez (2020), classrooms became more and more like microcosms of the global community in which we lived, with students from diverse socioeconomic, linguistic, and cultural backgrounds. In addition to improving learning outcomes, teachers who were adept at navigating this diversity also helped children develop a sense of inclusivity and respect for one another. Proficiency in diversity management required not only subject matter expertise but also a deep understanding of instructional approaches tailored to various learning capacities and styles. It also required empathy, cultural awareness, and the ability to establish a safe, welcoming environment where every child felt valued and encouraged to participate. While acknowledging this achievement, it was important to remember that maintaining a high standard of performance in diversity management was an ongoing effort.

2.4 Curriculum Planning

The teaching performance level among Social Studies Teachers as to Curriculum Planning was **Very Good (3.64)**. The indicator “Aligning teaching methods and assessment tools to learning objectives” obtained the highest mean score of 3.71 and was interpreted as **Very Good**. However, the indicator “Collaborating with other professionals to enrich knowledge and learning practice” garnered the lowest mean scores of 3.62 and was verbally interpreted as **Very Good**.

It implies that high performers are able to instruct learners in the subject in an efficient manner. They probably have the ability to make difficult ideas understandable, involve pupils in educational activities, and foster a supportive learning atmosphere. A high degree of teaching performance indicates that educators are successfully coordinating their lessons with the curriculum's aims and objectives. They are skilled in creating classes that address these learning objectives and have a thorough understanding of what pupils should learn. Effective teachers are frequently more flexible.

Based on changing educational standards, new trends, or the needs of their students, they can modify their pedagogical approaches. This flexibility guarantees that the curriculum will always be current and sensitive to the demands of the students.

As stated in Brau (2020), adhering to a set curriculum, social studies teachers were skilled in creating courses that aligned with the goals of the curriculum, ensuring that every teaching opportunity significantly advanced student's overall growth. Furthermore, a performance level this impressive suggested a dynamic approach to instruction. Instead of being restricted by memorization techniques, these teachers were adaptable and creative, customizing their lessons to meet the requirements and styles of a wide range of students.

The flexibility in the curriculum ensured that it remained interesting and current, fostering a culture of inquiry and discovery in the classroom. This accomplishment spoke volumes about the high professional standards of Social Studies teachers, showcasing their dedication to lifelong learning and growth beyond the curriculum's confines. By continuously adapting and innovating, these educators created more engaging educational experiences for their students, nurturing curiosity and enhancing overall learning outcomes.

2.5 Assessment and Reporting

The teaching performance level among Social Studies Teachers as to Assessment and Reporting was **Very Good** (3.66). The indicator "Using assessment data to improve classroom practice and learning" acquired the highest mean score of 3.68 and was interpreted as **Very Good**. However, the indicator "Effective feed-backing on learners' performance" yielded the lowest mean scores of 3.64 and was verbally interpreted as **Very Good**.

Table 2.5

It suggests that social studies instructors in private schools in Calamba City are using methods, techniques, and strategies that work well to improve student learning and engagement. It implies that the teachers have set up explicit and open processes for informing pupils and their parents/guardians of their evaluation outcomes. By doing this, it is made sure that everyone who could be affected by the students' success is aware of it.

Conforming to Almagro (2023), the component of reporting that built a connection between the classroom and the community at large was equally important. Reporting procedures that were clear and educational encouraged parents, stakeholders, and students to participate fully in the educational process. Teachers fostered a culture of collaboration and support, allowing constructive dialogue and enabling informed decision-making by ensuring that assessment outcomes were communicated clearly. The phrase spoke to greater societal objectives in addition to the direct ramifications for the educational context. The foundation of societal advancement, equity, and empowerment was education. Teachers who performed at a very high level demonstrated a shared

commitment to the development of human capital, which paved the way for the creation of informed, competent, and politically involved citizens. It emphasized how important institutional support, ongoing professional growth, and policy frameworks were.

2.6 Community Linkages and Professional Engagement

The teaching performance level among Social Studies teachers as to Community Linkages and Professional Engagement was **Very Good** (3.58). The indicator “Learning the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers” yielded the highest mean score of 3.69 and was interpreted as **Very Good**. However, the indicator “Linking with government agencies to promote learners’ welfare” attained the lowest mean scores of 3.36 and was verbally interpreted as **Very Good**.

It indicates that social studies instructors in private schools in Calamba City interact with the community in an active way to enhance their students' educational experiences. This could include working with neighborhood organizations, having speakers come in, planning field trips, or introducing regional topics into the curriculum. By fostering a sense of relevance and connectedness, these initiatives help students find greater meaning in their education. High levels of community connections suggest that pupils are being encouraged to develop civic engagement and awareness. Through the integration of classroom instruction with real-world concerns and community activities, educators facilitate students' growth in understanding and awareness of their civic responsibilities. Increased civic involvement and participation in neighborhood projects and decision-making processes may result from this.

As claimed by Kim (2019), the focus on professional engagement drew attention to how crucial innovation, teamwork, and ongoing learning were to the field of education. In today's globalized world, social studies educators who actively participated in professional development activities, interacted with their peers, and contributed to educational debates were better able to meet the changing demands of their students and address challenging issues. Within the educational community, professional engagement fostered a culture of lifelong learning and development, in addition to enhancing teaching effectiveness. Beyond its direct impact on education, the statement spoke to broader issues of social cohesion, community building, and democratic engagement. Education was not confined to the classroom; it also served to empower individuals and promote positive social change.

Research Question 3. Is there a significant relationship between 21st Century Teaching Strategies and teaching performance of Social Studies teachers in Calamba City private schools?

A significant relationship was present between 21st Century teaching strategies and teaching performance of Social Studies teacher. As shown in the probability values were all 0.000 which was less than the level of significance at .05, thus the null hypothesis was rejected. There was moderate to high positive correlation 21st Century teaching strategies and teaching performance as shown in the r values between .600 to .800.

It indicates that there is an extensive relation between the 21st Century Teaching Strategies and Teaching Performance. This also indicated that the more, the 21st Century Teaching Strategies, the better the Teaching Performance.

It emphasizes how instructional techniques in social studies education need to change. It gave attention to how crucial it was to incorporate contemporary teaching strategies that prioritize digital literacy, teamwork, critical thinking, and problem-solving. Teachers must modify their methods of education to meet the needs of the 21st-century learning environment.

Based on Ononiwu (2023), by adopting cutting-edge pedagogies like inquiry-based learning, project-based learning, and technology integration, educators cultivated critical thinking, teamwork, and adaptability, in addition to delivering knowledge. This demonstrated the transformative potential of pedagogical approaches that transcended conventional didactic techniques. Furthermore, the link pointed to a mutually beneficial relationship between the adoption of modern teaching methods and the effectiveness of education. Teachers were in a better position to engage students and promote deeper comprehension when they used 21st-century tactics to create dynamic and interactive learning environments. Consequently, this led to improved teaching effectiveness as measured by various criteria, including student achievement, classroom engagement, and the development of critical thinking skill.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are reached in light of the study's aforementioned findings:

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1. That the Social Studies Teachers use 21st Century teaching Strategies in their classroom is to modify instructional strategies to fit the changing requirements and preferred methods of learning of every generation. This accomplishment shows a dedication to teaching kids digital literacy, critical thinking, and global citizenship so they have the tools they need to prosper in a world that is becoming more interconnected by the day.
 2. That teachers who have been using 21st-century teaching methodologies have noticed a considerable rise in student engagement. Students' interest and passion for learning about historical events, civilizations, and societal challenges have been piqued by engaging in activities like multimedia presentations, online research projects, and cooperative debates. Teachers have seen notable gains in their students' critical thinking abilities by incorporating interactive learning environments and technological resources into their teaching. Students now routinely analyze original sources, weigh many points of view, and synthesize data

from a variety of digital sources, which encourages deeper comprehension and analysis.

3. That teachers in private schools usually use interactive teaching strategies to encourage pupils to participate actively in their education. They include debates, group discussions, and practical exercises to promote the development of communication, teamwork, and critical thinking abilities. At their classes, many social studies teachers at private schools place a high value on inclusivity and diversity. They employ inclusive teaching strategies, which include utilizing a variety of teaching resources, appreciating and respecting the unique experiences and viewpoints of their students, and providing chances for every student to participate and thrive.
4. That the association between a social studies teacher's success in the classroom and 21st-century teaching methodologies is significant since it reveals a significant shift in educational paradigms. This relationship highlights the critical significance that cutting-edge pedagogical strategies have in creating successful learning environments in the field of social studies education.

Recommendations

The researcher suggests the following in light of the above-mentioned findings and conclusions:

1. Technology Integration Specialists or Educational Technology Coordinators may promote the use of online resources and tools that facilitate interactive education. These may be collaborative projects utilizing educational apps and platforms, virtual reality field trips, or online simulations of historical events. They may stress the value of relating what is learned in the classroom to current affairs and concerns in the real world. In order to promote critical thinking abilities and global citizenship, they may also encourage pupils to examine current events through a historical or global perspective.
2. Administrators and Professional Development Coordinators may acknowledge social studies teachers who demonstrate a solid grasp of their subject and efficient teaching strategies. They may provide enrichment workshops with these knowledgeable teachers as the leaders, with an emphasis on the sharing of knowledge, tactics, and resources among peers. Also, they may plan workshops that address a range of social studies topics, such as political systems, concepts of geography, historical events, and cultural practices. Every module may go deeply into the material while offering useful teaching strategies and interesting resources. Moreover, they may incorporate practical exercises and case studies to demonstrate efficient teaching techniques in

the workshops. Lastly, they may urge participants to engage in dialogue, brainstorm, and work together to create creative strategies for instructing difficult subjects.

3. Librarians or Media Specialists may provide educators with a range of primary and secondary resources pertaining to the selected subjects. These may be documents from the past, videos, books, or articles. They may also encourage a climate in the classroom where students are at ease sharing their thoughts and having meaningful conversations. Additionally, they may stress the value of providing constructive criticism and engaging in active listening.
4. Professional Development Coordinators or Curriculum Specialists may organize workshops for professional development that will teach educators about the fundamentals and advantages of authentic assessment. With this, they may give students examples of assessment tasks that require them to use their social studies knowledge, such as research projects, role-playing games, and discussions. They have to make sure that the learning objectives and assessments are in line with each other. They should work together with educators to create assessment assignments that gauge students' aptitude for critically thinking in real-world situations, analyzing historical events, and assessing sources. To track students' progress and give timely feedback, teachers should receive training on the use of formative assessment tools like exit tickets, quizzes, and class discussions.
5. Community Engagement Coordinators may start a needs assessment and community mapping exercise to find historical places, cultural icons, and local resources that can improve the Social Studies curriculum. They have to involve parents, community members, educators, and students in this process to make sure that all points of view are taken into account. Also, they may invite guest lecturers or presenters for Social Studies classrooms from the local community, local historians, cultural specialists, and government leaders. These people have direct information, personal experiences, and insightful opinions about the history, culture, and current events of the community.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured that the ethical consideration was appropriately observed in all aspects of the research process. The objectives of the inquest were conveyed comprehensively to the school heads and teachers. School heads and teachers were acquainted through the letter with the task they would be extending for the success of the study. It also emphasized they would not be obliged to contribute to the survey, especially if it is against their will. The collected questionnaires will be handled accordingly to ensure the confidentiality of the information and safeguard the identities of the respondents. Likewise, the works of different bodies in this study were recognized and referenced.

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